

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN OPTIMIZING PRODUCTION COSTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses how the implementation of digital economy tools for industrial enterprises can reduce time to market, improve the quality of products and services, and enable new business models, which can help manufacturers improve production processes, reduce costs, and increase their competitiveness in the market.*

Keywords: *digital economy, business model, Industry 4.0, IoT sensors, Artificial intelligence.*

Introduction. Digital transformation in production means the integration of digital technologies, processes, and data throughout the entire production value chain:

- Optimizing business operations
- Increase efficiency
- Increase customer satisfaction

They achieve this by automating manufacturing processes, collecting and analyzing data, and facilitating rapid decision-making—using tools such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, and cloud computing. It helps manufacturers to improve production processes, reduce costs, and increase their competitiveness in the market.

The Internet of Things provides companies with new means of collecting reliable information about the state of production processes and allows for human factor monitoring with minimal costs and risks. Robotization and virtual and augmented reality technologies will have the strongest impact on the transformation of production models. 3D printers bring the manufacturer closer to the consumer and allow the production of products in a short period with a small batch.

Digitalization is revolutionizing the global economy. The introduction of digital economy tools for industrial enterprises provides an opportunity to reduce the time of goods entering the market, improve the quality of products and services, and use new business models. In the industry, tools of the digital economy mean the means of digitizing all physical assets of the enterprise and integrating them into digital ecosystems with the information of the enterprise's business partners. In practice, such tools represent a wide range of new technologies.

A prerequisite for the integration of an industrial enterprise into the digital economy is the introduction of a single information space into production, with the help of which enterprise management systems and industrial equipment can exchange information promptly. Industry 4.0 is a set of relations that arise in production processes related to the penetration of digital technologies (Industry 4.0) aimed at increasing the competitiveness of the country and business. In contrast to the German state initiatives aimed at the Internet of Industry, the term "Industry 4.0" for the Republic of Uzbekistan means the digital transformation of all sectors of the economy. According to Luding von Bertalanffy's general systems theory, every system has inputs and

outputs that change processes and feedback. Suppose we explain the meaning of the term "Industry 4.0" in the language of systems theory. In that case, the following should be understood: "Industry 4.0" is a chain of production processes in which the digital exchange of information between system links (people, machines, DATA centers) using online technologies is considered a necessary element. is a system consisting of a "Digital economy? Taking into account the amendments to the "Uzbekistan" program, it can be said that Industry 4.0 is a set of relations that arise in production processes during the penetration of advanced "end-to-end" innovative technologies in all sectors of the economy aimed at increasing the country's competitiveness. E-commerce technologies should be understood as methods of conducting e-commerce, mechanisms, and means of e-commerce management aimed at ensuring profit growth [1].

Digital transformation in the manufacturing industry is the use of technology to create a more efficient and customer-centric manufacturing environment, enabling companies to stay competitive and adapt to the changing business landscape.

Digital transformation in manufacturing helps companies optimize their operations, improve quality, increase efficiency, and create new business models by leveraging digital technologies and data.

The main part. Manufacturers can automate repetitive tasks, reduce errors, and improve efficiency by digitizing processes and operations.

Digital technologies such as IoT sensors and automation can help reduce the time required for product development, testing, and delivery.

Manufacturers can easily optimize workflows and improve communication between departments by using digital technologies. Here are some reasons why digital productivity is important in manufacturing:

- Faster time to market
- Improved quality
- Increased productivity

Digital transformation helps manufacturers gain insight into customer behavior and preferences, allowing them to create customized products and services. This can lead to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

In today's competitive market, manufacturers must focus on meeting the needs of their customers and providing a great customer experience to stand out from the competition. A good customer experience in manufacturing is essential for the following reasons:

- Increase customer satisfaction
- Increased income
- Improved brand image

Using digital technologies such as AI, machine learning, and big data analytics, manufacturers can gain new insights into their operations, identify areas for improvement, and develop new products and services.

By using digital technologies and data, manufacturers can gain new insights into their operations, identify areas for improvement, and develop new products and services. Today's factory with digital technology is very different from the leading factory of ten years ago. Advances in data and analytics, AI and ML, and technology vendors in the marketplace mean manufacturers can choose from hundreds of potential solutions and technology applications to improve the way they work.

Successfully implemented, these solutions provide irreversible returns. It leads to a 30-50% reduction in machine downtime in various industries, a 10-30% increase in production capacity, a 15-30% improvement in labor productivity, and an 85% more accurate forecast [2].

Industry 4.0 is the fourth wave of the industrial revolution in the United States. Industry 1.0 started with mechanization and 2.0 brought us mass production. With the advent of computerization in manufacturing, Industry 3.0 has taken its place. In Industry 4.0, computers and automation come together in entirely new ways, using robotics, machine learning, and manufacturing software to control production through autonomous machine decisions.

According to Forbes, for a developer to be considered 4.0, it must include:

- Interoperability: Machines, devices, sensors, and people need to connect and communicate with each other.

- Information transparency: Computer systems create a virtual copy of the physical world using sensor data to contextualize information.

- Technical assistance: Machines must support humans in decision-making and problem-solving and can assist or replace humans in tasks that are too difficult or dangerous.

- Decentralized decision-making: A cyber-physical system should be able to make simple decisions on its own to be as autonomous as possible.

It is designed to connect embedded system manufacturing technology with intelligent manufacturing processes. This is particularly evident in manufacturing variability, which allows businesses to better understand and understand processes, products, and even customer usage and behavior.

With Industry 4.0 systems in place, organizations can collect real-time information across the entire supply chain from start to finish. Machines quickly process and analyze data and use the results to improve operations, designs, and even products themselves through near-instant feedback.

Companies that adopt a digital-first mentality will be more prepared for the next industrial revolution.

Digital transformation is revolutionizing all aspects of manufacturing, affecting not only processes and productivity but also people. The right use of technology can lead to more empowered decision-making; new opportunities for training, retraining, and functional cooperation; better attracting and retaining talent; and improving workplace safety and employee satisfaction.

Customers will see the impact through reduced lead times, better first-time launch management, and improved customer service and complexity management. And of course, there are the win-win benefits of reduced environmental impact, made possible by less waste and waste and more efficient use of energy, water, and raw materials.

Implementing these productivity, process, and people improvements is not easy – especially in a network of separate manufacturing sites, each with its own site leadership, IT infrastructure, and workplace culture. It is not uncommon to hear of companies achieving impressive results through pilot programs at one plant site, only to fail to replicate these local successes across their network.

This was the case in a global industrial company. Faced with a significant increase in demand – doubling volume in just three years, leading to the production of more than 50 million additional parts – the business embarked on a massive digital transformation in a single factory.

The goal was to increase overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) by ten percentage points and reduce product unit cost by more than 30 percent.

While there are a variety of technologies that can be used in an organization, manufacturing operations have a few that need to be discussed in depth:

1. Cloud computing
2. Artificial intelligence
3. Machine learning
4. Internet of things
5. 5G
6. Blockchain
7. Digitization

Cloud computing - moving software systems and data to cloud-based servers.

This option consolidates infrastructure costs and allows companies to significantly share costs. Companies can also benefit from third-party services that offer cloud computing. Cloud computing allows your organization to scale quickly to meet changing business challenges.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) are algorithms that learn based on trends and behaviors and react without human interaction.

Modern cloud-based ERP solutions are now leveraging AI and ML capabilities in reporting, dashboards, and data analytics tools to succeed in this digital economy. Risk analysis can now be done with the help of artificial intelligence, which produces business predictions and forecasts based on real-time organized data, freeing up employees for other tasks.

The Internet of Things (IoT) is about connecting and creating intelligence from all the devices around us.

In industrial facilities, the IoT concept is implemented through mobile applications, digital cameras, digital scanners, and sensors. This information can then be stored, reported, or processed as needed and the system can respond accordingly.

5G connection - wireless connection at a speed of up to 10 Gbit / s.

It provides the upload and download speeds required for IoT systems, big data, and machine learning.

Blockchain technology is a method of secure data transfer with applications outside of the world of banking and finance.

It is now used in supply chain operations to ensure information security.

Digitization - Converting handwritten notes, documents, and pictures into a digital equivalent that can be received, processed, and stored by a computer

As you can see, digital transformation technologies are related to the collection and processing of large amounts of data. However, data is not useful if it is deleted and not available for decision-making. Digital transformation also requires providing real-time data across the entire organization. This, in turn, increases communication and interaction between different departments.

Data mining is one of the benefits of IoT. Every step of production can be monitored and studied. The result is a collection of "big data". The sheer volume of data is overwhelming, but it presents a world of opportunities for businesses to better manage their supply chain, improve day-to-day operations, and enhance customer relationships.

As companies move to a data-driven environment, there must be a system in place to manage data and processes. Implementing cloud-based ERP solutions integrates people, technology, and processes to become a connected business through digital technology and digital platforms. Cloud ERP software is flexible, intuitive, collaborative, automated, and intuitive, providing users with a single source of truth in real-time, accessible anytime, anywhere.

The use of technology in all operations increases operational efficiency. This allows the organization to quickly respond to a changing environment. It can change how a product is packaged, shipped, or even manufactured based on the information it collects. Automating business processes can help reduce errors and reduce costs. Digital transformation requires changing how businesses think about customers, products, and processes. This requires openness to evaluating data and flexibility to make changes based on data.

Digital transformation uses technologies like IoT to capture the data needed to customize product lines, tailor marketing, accelerate product improvements, and offer more effective customer service.

The technology offers cost savings and increased productivity as they are automatically alerted to system and machine errors. Manufacturers and distributors are experiencing reduced machine downtime, improved quality, less waste, and greater visibility through improved analytics.

Ways to reduce production costs and how digital transformation affects them:

1. Product design: Availability of product usage data allows manufacturers to improve product quality and design.

2. Lean manufacturing: Big data enables manufacturers to provide predictive rather than preventive maintenance. This reduces machine downtime and increases ROI on investment. Digital data about the production line can be collected and used to find problems and inefficiencies and recommend corrective actions. Timely and accurate information such as critical orders, material delivery delays, equipment failures, and inventory levels can be analyzed. Once analyzed, it can be used to optimize production schedules, demand forecasts, and lead times, leading to benefits such as inventory minimization, just-in-time production, and waste reduction.

3. Product standardization: using IoT, manufacturers can achieve "mass customization". This opens up opportunities for new service offerings without adding significant costs.

4. Product Line Rationalization: Good product cost information improves the ability to quickly understand profitability and optimize pricing.

5. Simplify supply chain management: A seamless flow of information for critical events across the supply chain between manufacturers, distributors, and customers facilitates response.

6. Total cost measurement: Big data opens the door to more opportunities to analyze costs throughout the production cycle and organization.

7. Focus on communications: Technology enables easy communication of critical information to improve vendor, partner, and customer relationships.

Digital transformation in manufacturing can significantly increase worker productivity. When you incorporate automated data collection into your business processes, you instantly free up time for your employees to work on other projects. In addition, automated data collection results in fewer errors and more efficient order fulfillment.[3]

Conclusions and Recommendations. Investing in technology and innovation is key for organizations today and is only one way to reduce costs. Even small companies must adapt to

increasing consumer demand and disruptive competition. The use of cloud computing software and digital tools directly contributes to financial management and control. From an operational perspective, technology has been used in many companies to optimize profitability and reduce costs.

One of the simplest and most effective ways to reduce costs within the company with the help of technology is to reduce material costs. A clear example is the transition to digital documents and efforts to make your organization paperless. Reducing the cost of paper, ink, printing, postage, and transportation can significantly reduce costs. Digitalizing manual and paper processes can also speed up the speed of doing business.

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